

Half-Metallicity in a BiFeO₃/La₂/3Sr₁/3MnO₃ Superlattice: A First-Principles Study

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Abstract : We present first principles results for the electronic, magnetic, and optical properties of the BiFeO₃/La₂/3Sr₁/3MnO₃ heterostructure as obtained by spin polarized calculations using density functional theory. The electronic states of the heterostructure are compared to those of the bulk compounds. Structural relaxation turns out to have only a minor impact on the chemical bonding, even though the oxygen octahedra in La₂/3Sr₁/3MnO₃ develop some distortions due to the interface strain. While a small charge transfer affects the heterointerfaces, our results demonstrate that the half-metallic character of La₂/3Sr₁/3MnO₃ is fully maintained.

Keywords : BiFeO₃, La₂/3Sr₁/3MnO₃, superlattice, half-metallicity

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